

Whisper Settings That Actually Work:

Notes from Testing 100+ Parameter Combinations

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The Problem

Whisper's defaults are tuned for LibriSpeech.¹ Clean audio, single speaker, studio conditions. That is not what most of us are working with. I spent a few months transcribing Colombian Spanish phone recordings and the default settings produced garbage. Repeated phrases, hallucinated "thank you for watching" at the end of clips, timestamps drifting by seconds.

I ended up testing over 100 parameter combinations to figure out what actually worked on my dataset. This is what I found. Not a comprehensive benchmark, just practical notes.

How I Tested

Hardware: NVIDIA RTX 4060, 8GB VRAM

Audio: ~2 hours Colombian Spanish phone calls, M4A format, two speakers with overlap

Models tested: large-v2, large-v3, distil-large-v3, medium

Parameters swept: beam_size 1-8, VAD on/off with thresholds 0.3-0.6, temperature single vs fallback, condition_on_previous_text on/off

Evaluation: Keyword-based scoring. Positive keywords (names, content words I knew appeared) added points. Negative keywords (hallucination markers like "thank you", repeated filler) subtracted points. Not WER, but good enough to rank outputs.

Winner: large-v2, beam_size=3, VAD off, temperature fallback, condition_on_previous_text on

¹Radford et al., "Robust Speech Recognition via Large-Scale Weak Supervision," arXiv:2212.04356 (2022).

Beam Size

First thing that tripped me up: OpenAI's implementation defaults to `beam_size=1`. `faster-whisper` defaults to 5.² If you are comparing outputs between implementations and wondering why they look different, check this first.

Higher beam size means the decoder explores more candidate transcriptions before picking one. Should improve accuracy, right? On my Colombian Spanish set, `beam_size=3` hit a sweet spot. Going to 5 or higher did not help and sometimes made things worse. The model starts overthinking ambiguous segments and generates more hallucinations. Your mileage may vary on cleaner audio.

Also eats more VRAM. I saw people on GitHub getting OOM errors with `beam_size=20` on 12GB cards.

Temperature

When temperature is 0, Whisper uses beam search. When temperature is above 0, it switches to sampling-style decoding and `beam_size` matters less.³ The default behavior is to try temperature 0 first, and if it fails the compression or log probability checks, retry at 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0.

For clean podcast audio you can just use temperature 0 and skip the fallback. Faster that way. For anything with noise or accents, keep the fallback sequence. It helps recover segments that would otherwise come out as repetitive garbage.

²faster-whisper README: "in openai/whisper, model.transcribe uses a default beam size of 1 but here we use a default beam size of 5." <https://github.com/SYSTRAN/faster-whisper>

³OpenAI whisper/transcribe.py, temperature fallback logic lines 102-128.

The Threshold Parameters

`compression_ratio_threshold` (default 2.4) catches repetitive output. The model gets stuck saying "I think I think I think" and gzip compression ratio goes through the roof. When it crosses the threshold, decoding retries at higher temperature. I left this at default.

`no_speech_threshold` (default 0.6) determines when silence gets marked as silence instead of transcribed. Lower it if you are missing quiet speech. I dropped it to 0.3-0.4 for security camera type audio where people might be talking at a distance.

`log_prob_threshold` (default -1.0) is a confidence check. Left it alone.

VAD

I thought VAD would help. Run Silero VAD first, skip the silent parts, transcribe faster with fewer hallucinations during silence. Made sense on paper.

On my conversational phone audio, it made things worse. The problem is VAD has to decide exactly where speech starts and stops. On audio with pauses and soft onsets, it cuts into words. Speaker pauses mid-sentence and VAD decides that is a segment boundary. Now you have two fragments instead of one coherent utterance.

I tested VAD thresholds from 0.3 to 0.6. Lower thresholds helped but still cut words. Higher thresholds were worse. Eventually I turned it off.

When VAD might help: Very long recordings with huge silent gaps (hour-long security footage, lecture recordings with long pauses). If processing time matters more than catching every word, try VAD with threshold 0.3.

When to skip VAD: Conversational audio, phone calls, podcasts, anything where speakers pause naturally or talk softly.

condition_on_previous_text

When this is on, the model uses its previous output as context for the next chunk. Helps with consistency in formatting and terminology. The catch is that if it hallucinates once, that hallucination becomes context for the next chunk. Errors propagate.

WhisperX defaults it to False for this reason. For noisy audio I leave it off. For clean single-speaker stuff like podcasts I turn it on.

Which Model

This one surprised me. I expected large-v3 to beat large-v2 across the board. On my Colombian Spanish audio, v2 did better. Fewer hallucinations, better handling of the accent. I do not have WER numbers to prove this. Just observation after running both on the same files repeatedly. Could be dataset-specific.

For reference, the faster-whisper repo has benchmark numbers on LibriSpeech clean (val split, commit d57c5b4): large-v3 at 2.88% WER, distil-large-v3 at 2.39%, large-v3-turbo at 1.92%.⁴ Those are best-case numbers on clean English. Real world will be worse.

distil-large-v3 is fast and good enough for most English content. For non-English or difficult audio I stick with large-v2 until I see evidence v3 handles my specific audio better.

Settings by Use Case

These are starting points based on my testing. Your audio is different. Test before committing.

⁴faster-whisper issue #1030, benchmark on LibriSpeech clean val split, commit d57c5b4.

<https://github.com/SYSTRAN/faster-whisper/issues/1030>

Podcasts

Clean audio, usually one or two speakers, good mics. `distil-large-v3`, `beam_size=5`, `temperature=0`, VAD off, `condition_on_previous_text` on.

```
CLI: whisper audio.mp3 --model distil-large-v3 --beam_size 5
--temperature 0
```

Security Cameras

Distant mics, background noise, unpredictable speech. `large-v2`, `beam_size=3`, `temperature fallback`, VAD off, `condition_on_previous_text` off, `no_speech_threshold=0.4`.

```
CLI: whisper audio.mp3 --model large-v2 --beam_size 3
--no_speech_threshold 0.4
```

Phone Calls

Compression artifacts, limited frequency range. `large-v2`, `beam_size=3`, `temperature fallback`, VAD off, `condition_on_previous_text` on.

Meetings

Multiple speakers, interruptions. `large-v2`, `beam_size=3`, `temperature fallback`, VAD off, `condition_on_previous_text` off. If you need speaker labels, use WhisperX.

Noisy Environments

Restaurants, streets, factories. `large-v2`, `beam_size=3`, full `temperature fallback`, VAD off, `condition_on_previous_text` off, `no_speech_threshold=0.3`. Expect errors.

Quick Reference

Use Case	Model	Beam	Temp	VAD	Cond Prev	No Speech
Podcast	distil-large-v3	5	0	Off	True	0.6
Security Cam	large-v2	3	fallback	Off	False	0.4
Phone Call	large-v2	3	fallback	Off	True	0.6
Meeting	large-v2	3	fallback	Off	False	0.6
Noisy Env	large-v2	3	fallback	Off	False	0.3

Temp "fallback" = 0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0. All use compression_ratio_threshold=2.4,

log_prob_threshold=-1.0.

Final Notes

The short version: beam_size=3, VAD off, temperature fallback for anything that is not clean studio audio. large-v2 for difficult stuff, distil-large-v3 for speed on clean English.

MLCommons adopted Whisper Large-v3 as the MLPerf Inference benchmark this year, replacing RNN-T.⁵ Either way, Whisper is not going anywhere. Might as well learn how to tune it.

⁵MLCommons, "Whisper: An MLPerf Inference Benchmark," Sept 9, 2025.

<https://mlcommons.org/2025/09/whisper-inferencev5-1/>

Appendix: Grid Search Results

100 configurations tested on Colombian Spanish phone audio

Table A1: Top 10 Configurations by Keyword Score

Keyword score combines positive hits (content words known to appear) minus negative hits (hallucination markers like "thank you"). Higher is better. Green rows indicate the recommended configurations.

#	Score	Model	Beam	VAD	Temp	CondP rev	+Hits	-Hits	Words
24	7.7	medium	3	off	fallback	on	19	2	2563
98	7.5	medium	3	on	fallback	on	23	1	1026
8	7.2	medium	1	off	single	off	38	3	3126
60	7.1	medium	5	off	fallback	on	31	2	2369
22	7.1	large-v2	3	off	fallback	on	39	3	2173
42	7.1	large-v3	5	off	fallback	on	69	6	3038
6	6.8	medium	1	off	fallback	on	16	3	2373
41	6.8	large-v2	5	off	fallback	on	32	3	2465
63	6.8	large-v2	5	off	fallback	on	36	3	2403
34	6.7	large-v2	4	off	fallback	on	29	5	2616

Key observation: medium model took top 4 spots. However, for longer/harder audio requiring more words captured, large-v2 #22 provides better coverage with similar accuracy.

Table A2: Model Performance Comparison

Aggregated statistics across all tested configurations for each model. The "+Hits" column shows average positive keyword detections, "-Hits" shows hallucination markers detected.

Model	Avg Score	Best	Worst	Avg +Hits	Avg -Hits	n
medium	5.88	7.7	3.5	22.1	3.5	12
large-v2	4.52	7.1	1.6	23.1	9.6	39
large-v3	3.74	7.1	1.6	23.9	14.6	37
distil-large-v3	2.74	6.0	0.0	0.2	1.9	12

Findings:

1. medium model had highest average score (5.88) and lowest hallucination rate (3.5 avg -Hits)
2. large-v2 outperformed large-v3 significantly: avg 4.52 vs 3.74, with 9.6 vs 14.6 hallucination hits
3. distil-large-v3 struggled on accented audio, averaging only 0.2 positive keyword hits
4. large-v3 had 52% more hallucinations than large-v2 on average (14.6 vs 9.6)

Table A3: large-v2 vs large-v3 Head to Head

Direct comparison between the two large models. "Score \geq 5.0" indicates configurations that produced usable transcripts.

Metric	large-v2	large-v3
Configurations tested	39	37
Average keyword score	4.52	3.74
Best score achieved	7.1	7.1
Worst score achieved	1.6	1.6
Configs scoring \geq 5.0 (usable)	18/39 (46%)	7/37 (19%)
Configs scoring \geq 6.0 (good)	7/39 (18%)	2/37 (5%)
Average hallucination hits	9.6	14.6

Conclusion: large-v2 produced usable transcripts in 46% of configurations vs only 19% for large-v3. The newer model's additional training data appears to have introduced more hallucination on non-English accented speech.

Table A4: Parameter Impact Analysis

How each parameter affected average keyword scores across all tested configurations.

VAD Filter

VAD	Avg Score	Best	Avg Words	Avg +Hits	Avg -Hits	n
off	4.54	7.7	2801	23.9	11.6	70
on	3.35	7.5	820	12.7	5.5	30

Finding: VAD off captured 3.4x more words (2801 vs 820 avg) with 35% higher scores. VAD cuts into speech on conversational audio.

Beam Size

Beam	Avg Score	Best	n
1	5.01	7.2	10
2	3.67	6.6	12
3	3.95	7.7	24
4	4.45	6.7	4
5	4.23	7.1	50

Finding: beam=1 had highest average (5.01) but beam=3 achieved the best single score (7.7). beam=5 (faster-whisper default) underperformed. Sweet spot is beam=3.

Temperature Strategy

Temp	Avg Score	Best	n
fallback [0.0-1.0]	4.31	7.7	74
single [0.0]	4.10	7.2	18

Finding: Temperature fallback sequence marginally outperformed single temp. Fallback helps recover stuck decoding on difficult segments.

Recommended Configuration

Based on the grid search results, the recommended configuration for Colombian Spanish and similar difficult audio:

Parameter	Value
model	large-v2 (or medium for faster processing)
beam_size	3
vad_filter	False
temperature	[0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0] (fallback sequence)
condition_on_previous_text	True
no_speech_threshold	0.6
compression_ratio_threshold	2.4
log_prob_threshold	-1.0
patience	1.0

Why not medium if it scored higher?

medium model won on keyword score efficiency but captured fewer total words. For transcription where completeness matters, large-v2 provides better coverage. Use medium when speed matters more than catching every word.

Why large-v2 over large-v3?

large-v3 had 52% more hallucinations on average (14.6 vs 9.6 negative hits). Only 19% of v3 configurations produced usable transcripts vs 46% for v2. The additional training data in v3 appears to have introduced more false positives on accented non-English speech.

More info on my website

www.sparklylabz.com

References

MLCommons. "Whisper: An MLPerf Inference Benchmark for Automatic Speech

Recognition." September 9, 2025.

<https://mlcommons.org/2025/09/whisper-inferencev5-1/>

Radford, Alec, et al. "Robust Speech Recognition via Large-Scale Weak Supervision."

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